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High-power test stand setup and final results of the high-power tests

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ABSTRACT

Work Package 7.4 aims to design, construct, and test two very high-gradient (above 150 MV/m at the cathode) C-band (5.712 GHz) electron RF guns. The first of these RF guns is a Standing-Wave (SW) type, featuring 2.5 accelerating cells, while the second is a multi-cell Traveling-Wave (TW) structure that incorporates the photocathode in the very first cell. This Milestone report presents details of the RF test stand and the results of the high-power tests conducted on the two fabricated guns.

I.FAST Consortium, 2025

For more information on IFAST, its partners and contributors please see <https://ifast-project.eu/>

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Executive summary

In this report, we summarize the activities related to the setup of the high-power test stand implemented at PSI, along with the final results of the high-power tests of the two photo-guns: the Standing Wave (SW) and the Traveling Wave (TW). Both devices operate in the C-band (5.712 GHz) regime and have been designed to achieve a cathode peak field above 150 MV/m.

The SW gun is a 2.5-cell standing wave cavity with a four-port mode launcher, designed to operate with short RF pulses (300 ns) and repetition frequencies greater than 400 Hz. Its realization was based on the new brazing-free technology developed and successfully tested at INFN. The gun has been high-power tested, reaching a cathode peak field of 160 MV/m without limitations due to the gun itself.

The TW gun is a unique 12-cell gun fed by on-axis coaxial waveguides, designed to operate with the very short pulse length of just 100 ns. The power dissipation within the gun is just 30% leading to a power dissipation of just 30W when operating at 100 Hz. The gun is currently undergoing high power conditioning and has reached its maximum power of 48.8 MW (without using the pulse compressor) equating to 146 MV/m. The conditioning will now move on to using the RF pulse compressor.

1 Introduction

RF photoguns are the most common electron sources for Free-Electron Laser (FEL) and Inverse Compton Scattering (ICS) facilities. They play a crucial role in such accelerator facilities and are currently primarily operated in the S-band regime (3 GHz). These S-band RF photoguns typically achieve cathode peak fields of 80-120 MV/m and repetition rates lower than 120 Hz. According to beam dynamics studies, the higher the peak electric field on the cathode, the better the quality of the beam emerging from the gun. For this reason, in the latest generation of RF guns, significant efforts have been made to increase the field amplitude while keeping the breakdown rate probability (BDR) under control. Higher values than the current 120 MV/m cathode peak field in state-of-the-art S-band guns would be highly desirable to further improve beam quality.

In this context, the possibility of implementing a full C-band injector is highly attractive, both for the beam parameters it can achieve and its compactness, as well as for the potential to operate at high repetition rates. Task 7.4 of the IFAST project focuses on the design, fabrication, and testing of two new radiofrequency (RF) photoguns operating in the C-band (5.712 GHz) frequency range.

Two different photoguns have been designed, fabricated, and high-power tested: a SW over-coupled cavity made of two-and-a-half cells, and a 11.5-cell TW accelerating section incorporating a photocathode in the very first half-cell. Both approaches are attractive, each with distinct advantages to be exploited, and warrant full experimental exploration.

The availability of a new state-of-the-art, compact, high repetition rate, and cost-effective electron injector would benefit a large portion of the accelerator user community, particularly facilities on the frontiers of beam quality, such as FEL radiation sources, Thomson/Compton photon sources, and plasma-based accelerators requiring external beam injection. Upgrades to existing machines and new projects based on normal-conducting RF and aimed at higher repetition rates to increase average beam current and event flux would also greatly benefit from this development. Compact dimensions, high flux, and cost-effectiveness expand the potential of these devices for industrial applications and small-scale research facilities.

2 High power test stand setup

To test the two RF photoguns, a new C-band high-power test stand was designed and commissioned at PSI. Prior to the development of this new RF photogun test stand, a klystron test stand remained in place after the SwissFEL injector test facility was moved to PSI's East Campus (Fig. 1). This klystron test stand was used to prepare klystrons for high-power operation in SwissFEL. Furthermore, the test stand also facilitated testing of concepts for SwissFEL, such as modifications to the low-level RF system. The klystron test stand features a 50 MW C-band Canon klystron (E37212) with a Scandinova modulator. The photogun test stand used this RF source to drive the high-power testing of the RF photoguns.

Building on the existing klystron test stand, the new RF photogun test facility recommissioned parts of the SwissFEL injector test facility bunker, adding new radiation shielding walls and a new Personnel Safety System (PSYS). The new bunker layout is shown in Fig.2, where the new shielding wall is highlighted in red. A girder, originally used to test the S-band photogun for SwissFEL and which remained in place after the injector test facility was relocated, was repurposed to support the new RF photoguns.

Before activating the test stand, it was crucial to understand the radiation generated within the bunker. The primary source of radiation in the test stand area is the dark current produced in the gun. This dark current can be lost either in the gun itself or on the electron beam dump, which is planned to be installed 2.3 m downstream from the gun. Fluxes of secondary particles resulting from electron losses were simulated using MCNP [1]. The CAD model of the bunker was converted into an MCNP model using the SuperMC program developed by the FDS team [2]. For efficient calculation of the photon and neutron flux attenuation by the thick shielding, variance reduction parameters were calculated using the ADVANTG software [3]. The resulting estimates of the prompt dose rate around the test stand (see Fig. 3) were compared with operational limits and ultimately used to develop an operational safety concept published in [4]. A comprehensive description of the test stand is found in [15].

Details of the waveguide network for the tests of the guns are provided in the following paragraphs.

Fig. 1: High power klystron-modulator and new bunker to test high power components.

Fig.2: CAD model of the new bunker developed for the test-stand with the gun and the dump mounted on the girder. Electron beam follows the z direction.

Fig.3: Dose rate from photons (pSv per 1 electron) on the horizontal (z, x) plane (view from the bottom of the bunker), for the losses on the gun (left) and on the dump (right).

3 Standing Wave Gun Test

3.1 DESIGN AND REALIZATION OF THE SW GUN

The electromagnetic and thermo-mechanical analysis have been already illustrated in a previous papers [5, 6] and the main rf parameters are reported in Table 1. The gun is a 2.5-cell structure and its design has been optimized to minimize the peak E field, the modified Poynting vector [7], the rf pulse length and pulsed heating [8]. For this reason, the gun has been designed with a coupling coefficient equal to 3 to allow operation with short rf pulses (300 ns) thus reducing the BDR, pulsed heating and the power dissipation. An elliptical profile of the iris with large aperture has been also implemented to reduce the peak electric field, to increase the frequency separation with the nearest $\pi/2$ -mode thus avoiding excitation of this mode with short rf pulses and to have a better pumping on the cathode cell. A four-port mode launcher [9] with an on-axis coupling has been also adopted to reduce the pulsed

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heating on the coupler and to have a perfect compensation of the dipole and quadrupole field components. The mode launcher has been also designed to integrate two pumping ports.

Table I: Main Parameters of the C-band Gun (in parenthesis there are those referred to the measured ones)

Parameter	value
Resonant frequency	5.712
$E_{\text{cath}}/\sqrt{P_{\text{diss}}}$ [MV/(m·MW ^{0.5})]	51.4
rf input power [MW]	18 (19)
Cathode peak field [MV/m]	160
Rep. rate [Hz]	100-400
Quality factor	11900
Filling time [ns]	166 (147)
Coupling coefficient	3 (3.5)
rf pulse length (t_p) [ns]	300
Mode sep. π - $\pi/2$ [MHz]	47 (48.3)
$E_{\text{surf}}/E_{\text{cath}}$	0.96
Mod. Poy. vector [W/ μm^2]	2.5
Pulsed heating [°C]	16
Average diss. Power [W]	250-1000

The gun has been realized without brazing, with the new technology developed at INFN and already adopted for the realization of RF photoguns in S-band [10-12]. The technology allows one to assemble the device using special gaskets in a clean room and to proceed, after the vacuum test, directly to the rf characterization. The main advantage is the possibility to use forged, not annealed, copper that, according to X-band high gradient tests and our tests on S band gun has been verified to exhibit extremely good performances in term of conditioning time and BDR. The gun realization procedure and the low power rf measurements results are illustrated in [13].

The gun, after the final assembly and vacuum test has been assembled in its final configuration with the solenoid and vacuum chambers as displayed in Fig. 4. The gun is followed by an emittance compensating solenoid and the laser injection chamber that allows a laser injection with the last mirror in air. Two pumping ports are integrated in the mode launcher and allow the system to reach a vacuum level of the order of 10^{-10} mbar/l sec without any bakeout. The gun integrates several different components: the standing wave (SW) cells, the four-port mode launcher and the copper cathode. The mode launcher has been machined using the five-axis milling machine Micron UCP600 Vario with precision on the internal dimensions of $\pm 8 \mu\text{m}$ and roughness below 200 nm. It has then been brazed in a vacuum furnace using palcusil 5 alloy. The SW cells and cathode have been machined using the lathe Schaublin 225 TM-CNC for the final finishing of the surfaces. The internal dimensions of the cells have been machined with a precision of $\pm 2 \mu\text{m}$ and a surface roughness below 30 nm. After the machining, the cells have been cleaned and assembled with the gun as illustrated in [13].

Fig. 4: Picture of the assembled gun with solenoid, vacuum system, support and vacuum chambers.

3.2 SW HIGH POWER RF TEST RESULTS

The whole system has then been transported to PSI and installed in the High-Power Test Stand. The picture of the gun connected to the C-band waveguide system and ready for the high-power test is illustrated in Fig. 5. The original gun feeding scheme foresaw the use of a new in-vacuum isolator. This device experienced some delays due to the difficulties encountered during its realization. For this reason, we have developed an alternative scheme using power dividers and a BOC-type pulse compressor already available at PSI as illustrated in [13]. A four-port power splitter outputs the RF power fed in with a power ratio of 1 to 9 at the two output ports. The power from the 10 % port is then compressed with the pulse compressor to increase the peak power. With this scheme, the reflected power from the cavity is split again with the same ratio allowing the reflected power to the klystron to be reduced to ≈ 500 kW. In the setup there are eight NEG-ion pumps and four directional couplers. The vacuum is also monitored through four vacuum gauges; one in the laser injection chamber, two near the BOC and one near the klystron window. These have been used to monitor the local vacuum in the regions expected to suffer the most from high power operation.

Fig. 5: The realized waveguide network and installed gun. (b) A diagram of the waveguide network.

Fig. 6: History of the input power, converted into a the peak cathode field (top) and vacuum pressure (bottom)..

After the first tests of the system and controls at high power in December of 2023, the RF conditioning began in February 2024 once the water system for the BOC was completed. The conditioning was done in a semi-automatic way, monitoring the vacuum at the different vacuum pumps and progressively increasing the power from the klystron and pulse length keeping the repetition rate at 100 Hz. In case of a vacuum discharge event, identified with a vacuum spike exceeding 3×10^{-8} mbar, the algorithm automatically interlocks the system. In the case of a reflected power to the klystron exceeding a 1 MW, the system also interlocks. During the interlock, the power is set to zero and the power ramped back to the level at which the system previously interlocked. The history of the input power, converted into a peak cathode field generated in the gun is shown in Fig. 6 [14]. In the same plot we have also reported the vacuum behaviour as measured by the vacuum gauges distribute in the waveguide transport line and laser injection chamber. In the first phase of the conditioning, the pulse compressor has been detuned by changing its temperature thus reducing the maximum input power into the gun. It is important to note that the conditioning has been dominated by the vacuum activity in the waveguide system and that the final maximum input power from the klystron has been limited by a vacuum activity in the ceramic of the klystron probably due to the reflected power from the system. In Fig. 7, we have reported the vacuum breakdown events in the gun and in the waveguide system. At the maximum input power we reached, so far, the calculated cathode peak field is about 160 MV/m with no limitation due to the gun. In the same figure we have also reported the cumulative number of breakdown events. Examples of the input signal into the gun and from the gun are given in Fig. 8. They have been compared with the calculated ones [14] showing a very good agreement.

Fig. 7: Break down rates as a function of the number of RF pulses (top) and cumulative breakdown events (bottom)..

Fig. 8: Gun input (top) and reflected (bottom) power compared with expectation..

4 Travelling Wave Gun Results

4.1 DESIGN AND REALIZATION OF THE TW GUN

The design of the TW photogun has been extensively reviewed in a previous submission and published in [16]. Therefore, here we will give a brief overview of its design. The travelling-wave rf photogun is a 11.5-cell C-band rf photogun with coaxial input and output couplers, featuring a load-lock capability achieved through a hollowing of the inner conductor of the input coupler. The RF design has been made to increase the peak cathode field to 25% greater than the on-axis field within the cells, and greater than the field of the irises. A comprehensive list of the rf parameters is given in Table 2. The coaxial input coupler is designed to have magnetic coupling slots which used for mechanical rigidity and allow for an exchangeable cathode, rather than its RF properties. The mechanical design is illustrated in Fig. 9.

Table 2 The RF parameters of the TW RF Photogun.

Parameter	Value	Units
Frequency	5.712	GHz
No. of Accelerating Cells	10+2	
Cell Length	17.495	mm
Structure Length	250	mm
Phase Advance per Cell	120	degrees
Attenuation	-1.41	dB
Group velocity	0.79	%c
Filling Time	90	ns
Input Power	82	MW
Peak E Field (Irises)	175	MV/m
Peak E field (Cathode centre)	200	MV/m
Peak H Field	558	kA/m
Pulsed surface heating (100 ns)	30.6	K

The TW photogun has been realised through a collaboration between PSI and VDL, in a similar means to the production of the SwissFEL C-band linear accelerator's structures. The UP machining was performed by VDL ETG in the Netherlands where each of the pieces for the TW gun was UP machined individually using milling and turning. The individual pieces were then transported to PSI where they were brazed together in several individual steps (Fig. 10). The final device was leak checked and is illustrated in Fig. 10.

Fig. 9: Rendering of the mechanical design of the Travelling-wave rf photogun with annotations of the major components.

Fig. 10: The realised .

4.2 TW HIGH POWER RF TEST RESULTS

At the conclusion of the high-power testing of the C-band SW gun, the C-band travelling-wave gun was installed in the test stand described above. The waveguide network was modified to remove the power divider as it was no longer required. The final waveguide network used is depicted in Fig 11.

We kept many of the NEG/ion pumps through the network to ensure good pumping on the 13 m waveguide network. Furthermore, a NEG/ion pump was added on each input and output coupler of the travelling-wave gun, as well as one in the load-lock system. The travelling-wave gun began high power conditioning on February 18th 2025 and conditioning has smoothly progress. Conditioning has started without the use of the pulse compressor, which was detuned by 18 K, using its temperature regulation system, in order to make it invisible to the waveguide network. With this configuration, we are able to achieve up to 45 MW into the TW photogun, with 5 MW lost to attenuation in the network. It is observed that the gun has reached a peak cathode field of 146 MV/m for a breakdown rate of $<10^{-5}$ bpp (Fig. 12). The next step in the conditioning will be to switch to using the RF pulse compressor.

Fig. 11: Diagram of the waveguide layout in WLHA for the testing of the travelling-wave rf photogun.

Fig. 12: Conditioning of the travelling-wave rf photogun.

5 Conclusion and Future plans

Two different radiofrequency electron guns operating at 5.712 GHz have been fabricated and high-power tested. The SW gun has exceeded a cathode peak field of 160 MV/m, while the TW gun has so far reached 147 MV/m, with continuous improvements. This latter device is still under testing. The SW gun will be installed at the INFN TEX facility as an innovative electron source for different types of experiments. The TW gun will continue to be tested to explore its performance limits in terms of cathode peak field and will be used in experiments such as field emission electron generation for industrial applications.

These new systems represent the forefront of RF photogun technology and enable operation at repetition rates above 400 Hz. The current goal is to generate and characterize the electron beam, demonstrating the full capabilities of these new, innovative electron sources.

6 References

- [1] D. Pelowitz (Ed.), MCNP6TM User's Manual, Version 1.0, Los Alamos National Laboratory, NM, USA, Rep. LA-CP-13-00634 Rev. 0, May 2013.
- [2] Y. Wu *et al.*, CAD-based Monte Carlo program for integrated simulation of nuclear system SuperMC, *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, vol. 82, pp. 161–168, 2015.
- [3] S. W. Mosher *et al.*, ADVANTG – An Automated Variance Reduction Parameter Generator, Oak Ridge National Laboratory, TN, USA, Rep. ORNL/TM-2013/416 Rev. 1, Aug. 2015
- [4] V. Talanov, Dose rate levels at the test setup for the I.FAST project in WLHA, Paul Scherrer Institut, Viligen, Switzerland, Rep. TM-81-22-1103, Dec. 2022.
- [5] D. Alesini *et al.*, “The New C Band Gun for the Next Generation RF Photo-Injectors”, in *Proc. IPAC'22*, Bangkok, Thailand, Jun. 2022, pp. 679–682. doi:10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2022-MOPOMS021
- [6] D. Alesini *et al.*, “Progress on the new high gradient C Band standing wave RF photo-gun”, in *Proc. IPAC'23*, Venice, Italy, May 2023, pp. 1374–1377. doi:10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2023-TUPA009
- [7] A. Grudiev, S. Calatroni, and W. Wuensch, “New local field quantity describing the high gradient limit of accelerating structures,” *Phys. Rev. Spec. Top. Accel Beams*, vol. 12, no. 10, Oct. 2009. doi:10.1103/physrevstab.12.102001
- [8] V. A. Dolgashev, “High magnetic fields in couplers of X-band accelerating structures,” in *PAC-03*. IEEE, 2003. doi:10.1109/pac.2003.1289674.
- [9] G. Castorina *et al.*, “A TM₀₁ mode launcher with quadrupole field components cancellation for high brightness applications,” *J. Phys. Conf. Ser.*, vol. 1067, p. 082025, Sep. 2018. doi:10.1088/1742-6596/1067/8/082025
- [10] D. Alesini *et al.*, “New technology based on clamping for high gradient radio frequency photogun,” *Phys. Rev. Spec. Top. Accel Beams*, vol. 18, no. 9, Sep. 2015. doi:10.1103/physrevstab.18.092001
- [11] D. Alesini *et al.*, “Design, realization, and high power test of high gradient, high repetition rate brazing-free S-band photogun,” *Phys. Rev. Accel. Beams*, vol. 21, no. 11, Nov. 2018. doi:10.1103/physrevaccelbeams.21.112001
- [12] V. Shpakov *et al.*, “Design, optimization and experimental characterization of RF injectors for high brightness electron beams and plasma acceleration,” *IEEE Open J. Instrum. Meas.*, vol. 17, no. 12, p. P12022, Dec. 2022. doi:10.1088/1748-0221/17/12/p12022
- [13] D. Alesini *et al.*, “Progress on the new high gradient C Band standing wave RF photo-gun”, in *Proc. IPAC'23*, Venice, Italy, May 2023, pp. 1374–1377. doi:10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2023-TUPA009
- [14] Alesini, D., et al. "Design, realization and high power RF test of the new brazed free C band photo-gun." *Proc. IPAC 24*: 2929-2932.
- [15] Lucas, T. G., et al (2024). Developments and first results from an RF test stand for high brightness C-band photoguns at PSI. In *Proceedings of the International Particle Accelerator Conference, IPAC 24*.
- [16] T. G. Lucas, et al., Toward a brightness upgrade to the SwissFEL: A high gradient traveling-wave rf photogun. *Phys. Rev. Accel. Beams* 26, 103401 10.1103/PhysRevAccelBeams.26.103401